

LOCAL AREA NETWORK SECURITY METHODS AND ASPECTS. SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW.

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ABSTRACT

Network security is a crucial aspect of information technology that protecting network devices being attacked by hackers. Another benefit of securing networks, especially local area network which is our main purpose, is assuring the accessibility, integrity, and confidentiality of information.

For protecting LAN and information within the LAN, we have driven a systematic literature review to get deeper information about network security methods and aspects. Besides these, we have learned how we can implement them in the real world. For doing that we have use Cisco Packet Tracer to examine each of the security methods to give a suggestion. For each method, we have configured a scenario and provided codes based on them. The common methods are port security, ACL, AAA and DHCP snooping.

In the literature review part, we have discussed them a lot by providing up-to-date research papers and online resources. As a methodology, we used systematic literature review.

For conclusion, we have summarized the information that provided in the literature review part. Also, we have gathered summary information from lots of research papers. Many of them suggested various kinds of methods to secure network. As a result, we concluded that providing LAN and information security is a long-term procedure and for this process it is recommended to use combination of methods. However, in terms of information security, DMZ, ACL, VLAN, STP and DHCP Snooping are more crucial aspects that we must consider, because each of them is vulnerabilities to access information. AAA method plays as a key role in protecting them within LAN.

INTRODUCTION

In our developing world, building internal and external networks is quite easy. But we must consider that when building a network, the security of information and the security of the network must be fully ensured. Setting up internal networks is a lengthy procedure, and many security steps must be taken. The security of the internal network plays a key role currently. Many measures should be taken to ensure security, such as installing a security system, securing ports, fully protecting the server, etc.

To apply what we said in real conditions, we must first use it in the network architecture. Network architecture consists of Access layer, Distribution Layer and Core Layer. There is a connection between each layer, and currently several measures are taken to prevent both internal failures and external attacks. At this time, we will discuss Access Control List, Port security, Whitelisting, Blacklisting, DHCP Snooping, AAA, DAI, DMZ, etc. for protection of LAN. These are the initial steps to ensure the security of local area network.

The primary aspect of information security is the secure construction of internal networks. Establishing a secure internal network is one of the primary factors of direct information security and its main security principles such as integrity, accessibility, and confidentiality.

Therefore, the main goal of preparing this article is to examine the methods and rules for ensuring the complete security of the internal network, as well as which methods of protection of information within the internal network are discussed. Besides these, for security application in terms of LAN, we made a network architecture in Cisco Packet Tracer. We will examine all LAN security methods to ensure LAN security and information security within LAN. By doing this, we will choose the proper actions and methods in Cisco Packet Tracer. Each of configurations has its own working codes in cisco IOS which is an operating system of cisco network devices.

For conclusion, we will discuss our examination and give suggestions towards security methods.

LITERATURE REVIEW

1. Network Security

All the measures required to preserve the integrity of a computer network and the data contained in it are referred to as "network security." Because it protects critical information from online threats and makes the network reliable and usable, network security is crucial. To defend consumers and companies from malware and cyberattacks like distributed denial of service, effective network security strategies include a variety of security tools.

Computers, servers, and wireless networks are just a few examples of the interconnected equipment that makes up a network. Many of these gadgets are open to attack. On a network or as software as a service, network security requires the employment of several software and hardware solutions. As networks get increasingly complicated and businesses rely more on their networks and data to operate, security becomes more crucial. As threat actors develop new ways to target these increasingly complex networks, security techniques must change (Luo, 2020).

Security is typically described as everyone's duty because every user on the network represents a potential vulnerability in that network, regardless of the specific method or business security plan (Barney & Letkevich, 2023).

There are lots of types of network security tools and software. The list contains more commonly used ones:

- Access control list,
- Antivirus,
- Email security,
- Firewall,
- Mobile security,
- Virtual Private Network – VPN,
- Web security,
- Wireless network security, etc.

2. Local Area Network Security

There are lots of aspects we should consider about LAN security. LAN security is a backbone of information security as well. While configuring security in LAN, there are lots of aspects that we must pay close attention to. According to the research of Francisti, Balogh and Koprda (2018), most of common types of attacks are DNS, SSL, Brute force, Browser, and DoS. While attacking to the LAN, hackers seek TCP/IP slack and packets to capture them. A single network segment or the entire

network can be observed by the packet sniffer. This is dependent on the placement and configuration of network switches. The packet sniffer can normally only record one channel at a time on a wireless network. If the packet has already been captured, the sniffer must analyze it and make it accessible to the attacker. The individual who analyzes the data can see specifics of communication between two or more network nodes.

2.1 LAN security methods

There are some objectives about vulnerabilities of LAN security (Cisco, 2023):

- LAN attacks,
- MAC attacks,
- Layer two attacks based on TCP/IP stack,
- Access control,
- Endpoint safety.

Nowadays, most attackers attack to endpoints of network, for examples of these attacks we can say DDoS which is attacking to a network from many devices. Another type is malware that assaults a network by injecting some malicious software and by doing that, information confidentiality, integrity and accessibility will fail. For protection in terms of endpoint safety, we can use VPN or Virtual Private Network that changes our public IP, NGFW or Next Generation Firewall which can do deep package inspection and even VPN can be failed in these kinds of firewalls, because, while deep package inspection, the destination and source IP will undo its native IP address, and the last one is Network Access Control or NAC. NAC contains Authorization that you can permitted to network, Authentication which you can do some limited action and Accounting that list of action that you have done. AAA principles that implement either Tacacs or Radius. Most companies use these techniques to prevent attacks to their LAN network. For protecting endpoint security, the preferable way is combining these techniques with email and web security (Shikarwar & Saxena, 2017).

to remotely access a PC and infect it with malicious software. Recently, SSH access attempts have been discovered that used SSH over DNS tunneling to get around network security measures (Lee & Lee, 2022). Port security is more about downing the ports of any switches automatically by code. While doing this, first all the MAC addresses should be installed into switches by their port number. If anyone inserts their device into the port which MAC address has already been applied to that, the port automatically protects, restricts or shutdown itself (Yang, Pan, & Su, 2022).

Figure 2: Port security enabled for all of three PCs.

In Figure 1, port security enabled for all of three PCs and each of them has configured different port security modes, such as, for fa0/1 protect, fa0/2 restrict and fa0/3 shutdown. Even though laptop connected to fa0/3 and green light appears, it cannot send any ping and even cannot get information. For each port should be accessible by switch, and each port has its own ports security mode. For this action, we used these codes:

```
(config) # int range fa0/1-24
```

```
(config-if) #switchport mode access
```

```
(config-if) # switchport port-security
```

```
(config-if) # switchport port-security mac-address sticky
```

```
(config) # int fa0/1
```

```
(config-if) # switchport port-security violation protect / restrict / shutdown
```

Third important security threat is Layer 2 attacks that mostly hold crucial aspects about LAN security. For example, VLAN, DCHP Snooping, MAC, ARP, STP, DAI and Port security. These are

threats that we should be careful about while constructing a secure network. With this attempt, we can enhance information security. Layer two concept contains two sub concepts such as MAC and LAN attacks which we have listed above. The most important concept is VLAN hopping. While making connection between two or more switches, trunking status has already been up which we call it DTP or Dynamic Trunking Protocol. This allows hackers to get confidential data by trunks to connect and attack the network. By prohibiting this, we should write down STP or Static Trunking Protocol. VLAN relies on IEEE 802.1Q standard. For routers, we use WLAN that we integrate GRE tunnel between two routers to pass their confidential network data for making proper connection (Koerner & Koa, 2016). This threat leads to the leaking of VTP, VLAN, MAC and IP information. Hackers use Kali Linux to force their laptops pretend as a switch to make a connection between switches over VLAN.

Figure 3: DTP is deactivated for VLAN attacks.

In Figure 2, we have deactivated DTP between switches by their ports by static trunking with this code:

```
(config)#interface fa0/24
```

```
(config-if) # switchport mode access
```

For securing LAN and information, ACL or Access Control List is used to network. ACL is a filtering method used at end-system firewalls, routers, or switch interfaces to enforce security. ACL filters data flows according to pre-established rules. Based on certain packet header values which contains source and destination IP of the packed, one or more predefined ACL rules determine the flow matching provisions. A switch discards or advances the flow depending on the ACL policy in place. ACL

regulations also make it possible to filter unauthorized flows early and adequately safeguard the essential services. Contrary to other ACL implementation methods, efficient implementation of ACL policies at switches' interfaces also aids in increasing network throughput, decreasing end-to-end data flow delay, and efficiently distributing the flows at the edge and backbone network (Ibrar, et al., 2021).

Figure 4: Standard and Extended ACL has been configured.

In Figure 4, we configured standard and extended ACL HQ router. Based on our purpose, we deny PC3 to ping another PC from New York branch to HQ as a standard ACL. Additionally, we added extended ACL to deny PC3 for using EIGRP routing to other PCs from Destination HQ. As you can see from the command line of PC3, PCs from HQ are unreachable. By doing this, we can secure accessibility and confidentiality of information as well. These codes were used for both standard and extended ACL configuration:

```
(config)# ip access-list standard HQACL
```

```
(config-acl) deny 192.168.2.2 0.0.0.255
```

```
(config-acl) # permit host 192.168.2.3 0.0.0.255 for standard ACL,
```

```
(config)# ip access-list extended HQACL
```

```
(config-acl) # deny eigrp 192.168.2.2 0.0.0.255 192.168.1.1 0.0.0.255
```

```
(config-acl) # permit eigrp 192.168.2.3 0.0.0.255 any for extended ACL.
```

Another common LAN threat is DHCP Snooping. While configuring DHCP service in a network, we allow other devices to easily connect to the service. While a new device connects to the DHCP service,

While showing DHCP snooping information, we can see which MAC address uses which IP address from the server. This is one of the best ways to secure LAN and information within it.

STP or Spanning Tree Protocol is a protocol that runs while connecting a cable with a switch between either a switch or a device. If the connection between switches is established, then STP automatically works to prevent loopback which failover the entire network. However, in most of the companies STP turns down between switches and PC devices, due to late internet connection that takes only 30 seconds to connect. However, tuning of STP is a bad idea and this leads to another LAN attack which is called STP attack. Again, in this attack, hackers use software to make their devices as a switch to fail the network and get valuable information. For preventing this attack, BPDU Guard uses to make a protection for closed STP ports. In this case, the port is turned on, due to green color of the port, however, the hacker cannot access the switch (Lin, Lin, Kong, & Guan, 2023).

Figure 6: For preventing STP attacks BPDUGuard activated

In Figure 5, we have deactivated STP, but to prevent STP attacks, we have activated BPDUGuard on 10 to 14 fast ethernet ports of Switch 3. Even if STP deactivated, Switch4 cannot access the Switch3. For this action we used these codes:

```
(config)# int range fa0/10-14
(config-if) # spanning-tree portfast
(config-if) # spanning-tree bpduguard enable.
```

There are other methods for securing LAN, such as DMZ, port forwarding, MAC filtering and Firewall. When discussing internet security, two terms that are frequently used are DMZ and port forwarding. The primary distinction between the two, even though they are both used in security, is

how they raise security. A DMZ is a limited area of a network that is freely accessible to the internet or other networks used by the public (Shih, 2022).

You can still utilize the internet without port forwarding because it is not actually necessary. When you need a third-party application to be able to connect to specific services on your computer, an issue occurs. Since the connection was not made from within, the firewall would automatically block it. When port forwarding is activated, the router will redirect requests made on a particular port to a certain machine on the network that can fulfill the request. If you want to run a web, email, or file server on your computer, port forwarding may be useful (Difference Between, 2023). The firewall is set up so that only connections from the inside network can access the outside and DMZ networks, but none of those networks can access the inside network. The outside network is unable to connect to the internal network, but it can connect to the DMZ. While the DMZ is unable to connect to the internal network, it can connect to the external network (Zhou, Rababah, & Bader, 2018).

A firewall is a security measure that guards against unwanted access or attacks on a computer or network. A firewall is a software or hardware device that sits between a local area network (LAN) and the internet and filters incoming and outgoing network traffic in accordance with a set of rules.

In a LAN context, there are many ways to construct a firewall, including (He, 2021):

- The simplest type of firewalling is packet filtering, which separates packets based on their source and destination addresses, protocols, and po
- By monitoring the status of network connections and only allowing packets that are a part of established connections to pass through the firewall, stateful inspection provides an extra degree of security to packet filtering.
- Application-level gateway: This technique offers a better level of security by checking each packet's contents to make sure they adhere to the protocol in use. For instance, a gateway that manages HTTP traffic at the application level would verify that each packet includes legitimate HTTP headers and content.
- Proxy server: A proxy server functions as a bridge between a local area network and the internet and can be set up to filter traffic according to predetermined criteria. Hardware or software can be used to construct packet filtering firewalls.

This is one of the basic types of firewalls. There are even firewalls that VPN cannot pass through which are Next Generation Firewalls. With their content awareness features, NGFWs, which are innovative cyber security devices, can address this problem. NGFWs are network and security devices, and it can be difficult to position one in a multicast network properly and test NGFWs for

their ability to avoid threats including web, malware, and exploit attacks (Uçtu, Alkan, Doğru, & Dörterler, 2021).

Lastly, we can discuss about white and black listing. Whitelisting is an allowance technique that gives access to the specific Ips in the LAN to get Internet as well as services. Blacklisting is more like deny to internet. The logic behind this security method is anti-phishing. The white-list, on the other hand, contains authentic and legitimate websites; however, just like the black-list, it is challenging to maintain a global whitelist. This is because the websites are numerous and rapidly expanding, making it impossible to create a database for a whitelist that contains all of the available sites (Azeez, Misra, Margaret, Sanz, & Abdulhamid, 2021).

CONCLUSION

Until now, we have discussed lots of LAN security methods to secure LAN itself, as well as the information withing it. There are lots of methods that we can give as a suggestion to build secure network. However, we should carefully choose every of them for our main purpose. Network security must be established using a layered strategy, with numerous lines of defense cooperating to offer complete security. In addition to rules and processes to guarantee that staff members and other authorized users adhere to best practices for security, this could involve both hardware and software solutions.

Based on our examination in Cisco Packet Tracer, DHCP snooping, Port security, Access Control List and AAA are main security methods in local area network. By using these methods, we can improve the accessibility, integrity, and confidentiality of information as well. In terms of STP and VLAN security, they also maintain security inside LAN network, but more like port related.

On the other hand, DMZ, port forwarding, white and black listing are crucial in terms of wireless network security in Local Area Network. When we build a web or email service, we should obey these rules to protect our services.

However, beside all these methods, firewall is also most powerful method to secure network and information. It consists of lots of tools to prevent unauthorized attacks from any hackers.

In general, network security is a field that is always developing, with new threats appearing frequently. Organizations should constantly analyze their security posture and keep up with the most recent security trends and technology to make sure they are effectively secured against both present and emerging threats. According to the many research articles that we collected, the final

suggestions is choosing right action to securing the network with the combination of these methods either protecting the network architecture or information security.

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